
D8.2 Digital Identity, Website and Social Media Deliverable

General information

Project name	AgroServ Integrated services supporting a sustainable agroecological transition
Deliverable D8.2	Digital Identity, Website and Social Media Deliverable
Work package	Work Package 8 (WP8)
Grant agreement n°	101058020
Call	HORIZON-INFRA-2021-SERV-01
Project duration	01.09.2022 - 31.08.2027 (60 months)
Project coordinator	Michel Boër michel.boer@anaee.eu
Dissemination level	Public
Main author	Work Package 8: the communications officer with the assistance of the communication board members and the CEREEP-Ecotron IdF team.
Date of approval	04/10/2023
Approved by	Management Board and Executive Board
Submission date	04/10/2023

Version history

Version n°	Date	Description
V1.0	27/09/2023	First version
V1.1	04/10/2023	Approved first version

Funded by
the European Union

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Executive summary

This deliverable is a public document of the AgroServ project delivered as part of the Work Package 8 (WP8). It focuses on the project visual identity and its presence throughout various digital channels which are considered as enablers in maximising the project impact as they allow better exploitation and dissemination of the project results.

The visual identity package presented in this document aims to guarantee graphic coherence and will help its reader understand the essential elements of the AgroServ visual identity. It will explain how those elements and channels will be used. It is important to respect the guidelines presented in this document to respect the project's approach in designing, implementing, and building its different communications actions.

We have defined the visual identity of the document by a collection of design elements, including the project logo, the colour scheme, the project website, the various templates, and publicity materials (reports, presentations, videos, brochures).

An introduction to different visual elements is presented in this deliverable, including the foundational elements of the project logo, the colour palette, the guidelines for the appropriate use of the visual elements, the templates, the social media sites (Twitter and LinkedIn) and publicity materials (goodies, promotional videos, info-packs).

It should be noted that a "Project identity kit" including these and all other visual elements of the project will be made available to all consortium members and to partners.

Introduction

This document presents the initial deliverable about the project's visual identity. A professional designer has been contracted to create a logo for the project to enable easy and clear recognition of the project AgroServ. The visual identity associated with this logo will be respected and implemented on all communication materials. All dissemination materials produced within the project will be designed in line with the visual identity. Logos, typography, graphic elements, branding guidelines and templates are available for partners to access and download from our Nextcloud (internal platform).

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the European Union

Graphic elements

A series of graphic elements and branding items were developed to represent the project and to support a consistent “look and feel” and messaging across communication outputs.

The AgroServ logo¹

The AgroServ logo builds on and reflects the core content of the project:

¹ Designed by Céline Lavalade, *CelineIgraphe* (graphic designer).

Item Overview

Partnership, Trans-disciplinarity

Living
beings,
Ecology

12 european entities

FONT

Gill Sans bold

(with white lining) baseline

Myriad Pro Condensed

although most of the wording is readable in 7pt, baseline is recommended with lowercase height (an 'n' or an 'e') = 2 mm ≈ 11.5 pt.

Light version, without baseline
for badge, smaller spaces

minimum height recommended = 22 mm
Papier / *PRINT*

The colour palette

To represent the AgroServ project, a bright and flexible palette that uses vibrant saturation has been chosen. These colours are related to the research areas and subjects covered by the project (agronomy, natural sciences, climate, energy, aquatic ecosystems, etc.) and are appealing to its target audience. The supporting colours (black and grey) have been selected with the same precision to work in support of the principal colours (green, orange and blue). All colours have been selected to work well in combination with each other and to enable a full range of visually engaging communication.

Colors

Black 100%
Gray B 60%

CMJN (37, 10, 100, 1)
RVB(180, 189, 0)
#B4BD00

Pantone 390C

Main color: *green*

**Agronomy,
nature**

CMJN (0, 47, 89, 0)
RVB(245, 154, 40)
#F59A28

Pantone 1375C

Complimentary color : Orange

Climate, Energy

CMJN (100, 54, 0, 0)
RVB(0, 92, 185)
#005CB9

Pantone 300C

Secondary color : *blue*

**Ecosystem
Aquatic,
Aquaculture**

Simplified use for 3 color screen printing/embroidery
(except digital transfer - cmjn)

P. 390 C
P. Black process

P. Cool gray 10 C

Black and white

Gray B 40%

Black 100%
Gray B 60%

Gray B 30%

minimum height = 22 mm
Paper / PRINT

NIGHT MODE

Minimum
width 26mm

Gray B 30%

Attention to the change
of support size (responsives sites)
Screen / WEB

Width 150 px minimum
Screen / WEB

**On a dark background, or a strong gradient,
the baseline can be white or remain grey if there is enough
contrast.**

Avoid putting the visual in color on/ NO TONE ON TONE

- tone on tone
- gray
- mustard yellow
- purple
- medium blue
- green
- multicolor
- patterns

The AgroServ goodies

In order to ensure greater visibility of the project during events that are organised by the project or to which the project is participating to engage with its current and potential stakeholders and enlarge its community, goodies that respect the graphic identity of the project can be used.

Goodies prepared for the first conference organised by AgroServ (European Research Services on Agroecology Conference, ERSAC2023):

Other publicity and promotional items that can be prepared for future events (agricultural community, etc.):

Advertising and corporate branding

> For communication purposes, the baseline can be moved and enlarged

It's allowed!

> It is normal and possible that the technical constraints of marking implies small modifications in the details in the details (thickness,...)

engraving

> The provider may have to adapt the colors "as close as possible" according to its supplies marking supplies

Typography and Templates

Distinctive and powerful typography reinforces the project's visual identity, adds character to key messages and enables communication with target groups more effectively. For the AgroServ project, the Arial font family was selected and the visual identity of AgroServ has been implemented in developing templates for internal and external purposes. For instance, here are some examples of PowerPoint presentations developed for the project:

The AgroServ Website²

The AgroServ official website was launched in **September 2023³**. The sitemap is organised into **four main sections**:

1	About	AgroServ, in a Nutshell (published)
		Our Commitments (published)
		Our Research Infrastructures (published)
		Our European Partners (published)

² For editorial information, please refer to our [Legal Notice page](#). The technical aspects related to setting up the website were taken care of by the CEREEP-Ecotron IdF team.

³ A temporary version of the website was made available from June 2023 to September 2023 to ensure continuity of the activities. Information was also published on ERSAC's website created to disseminate information related to AgroServ's first conference on research services that took place in June in Prague and online.

		Organisation and Contact (published)
2	Research services	Explore our Catalogue (published)
		Explore our Guidelines (published)
		Scientific domains (published)
3	Calls and Applications	Application Procedure (published)
		Ethics and Data Policy (published)
		Frequently Asked Questions (published)
4	Outreach & Impact	Newsroom (published)
		Knowledge Transfer (published)
		Scientific Publications (published)
		Transdisciplinary Initiatives (upcoming) <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Related Initiatives • Related Projects
		Resources (upcoming) <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Media toolkit • Deliverables • Glossary of terms

When drafting and organising contents for the website, certain rules were identified and followed to optimise the user experience, avoid high exit rates, and publish contents that are appealing and attractive to our stakeholders:

Communicating ideas clearly

- Adopt an economical style and relevant writing techniques that reduce the idea to its essence for quick readability and maximum effectiveness.
- Avoid redundancy, long-winded constructions, superfluous details, fancy language, and excesses.
- Simplify complex ideas and express them in an evocative way to facilitate understanding, but without making them very familiar or down-to-earth.
- Enhance the elegance of texts with contextual additions to make your ideas punchier and give rhythm to the text.

- Adopt editorial techniques to enhance legibility and reading speed by eliminating any source of visual distraction that reduces immediate memorability: double negatives, unnecessary forms of ceremony (capital letters, etc.).
- Keep repetition if it's justified but remove it if it impoverishes the quality of the text.
- Avoid technical jargon and language that should be used on internal communication channels. Simplify ideas and when needed update the glossary of the technical terms on the website and the application portal (ISIA Portal) to avoid using the technical jargon and losing readership.

Giving meaning to texts

- For each publication, think about:
 - * The target audience
 - * The issue/subject you're addressing (what the readers need to know)
 - * The objective (the actions you want your community of users to take after reading the text)
 - * The added value for the community
- Choose the type of publication and the relevant communication channel to ensure effective communication (for example, opt for a simple tweet rather than a two-sentence news article).
- Emphasise the uniqueness and singularity of the website's publications (avoid copy-pasting from other partner sites).
- Think about the website's evolution and the continuous improvement of the sections or pages (don't forget micro-content such as sitemaps and page headings).

Reducing the environmental footprint of web content

- Only use the resources needed
- Respect pre-defined image sizes
- Recycle your pages and update them if they're not in use and don't need to be archived, rather than creating new ones (e.g. news and events).

“ For each publication, think about...
your target audience!

Homepage

- * Header/Main navigation
- * News Banner (3 news items)
- * The 11 Research Infrastructures at the heart of AgroServ
- * The AgroServ Ecosystem
- * Social Media Links
- * Contact details
- * Footer

Upcoming: “You are” buttons (personalised content for each identified profile of stakeholder: farmer, scientist, business, citizen, media, other)

— AgroServ, in a Nutshell

[Home](#) • [ABOUT](#) • [AgroServ, in a Nutshell](#)

AgroServ, in a Nutshell

Ensuring a viable agroecological transition towards sustainable and resilient agri-food systems

AgroServ is a **transdisciplinary project (2022-2027)** funded by the European Union under the **Horizon Europe** programme. It aims to **grow the agroecology research community** through supporting the **cross-fertilisation of knowledge** in a variety of fields: agricultural sciences, natural sciences, biological sciences, ecology, forestry, fisheries, agronomy, etc.

Agriculture improves **health and wellbeing**. It contributes to **local food security**, increases farmers' incomes and helps **reduce poverty**. However, developing a resilient and sustainable agricultural system can be challenging. Success hinges on a deep understanding of the systems and their interactions with the environment.

The **EU-funded AgroServ** project will study the **threats and challenges** and deepen our understanding of how to achieve a resilient and sustainable agri-food system. This project will bring together all actors of the agriculture system. Farmers are the first, thanks to a wide offer of living labs across Europe.

#Transitione
#Agroecology
#HorizonEurope
#SustainableAgriculture

A Europe-wide data ecosystem

A unique offer of research services

AgroServ, in numbers...

AgroServ, in a Nutshell

- * Presentation of the project
- * Key information and figures

— Our Commitments

[Home](#) • [ABOUT](#) • [Our Commitments](#)

Our Commitments

Agroecology, a path to sustainability

AgroServ aims to provide the scientific community with **large, high profile research services** to facilitate and enable **interdisciplinary and transdisciplinary research in agroecology** and foster open science and innovation.

To address **current and emerging global challenges**, AgroServ is born from the need of a **collective action** capable of enhancing the sustainability of food systems, safeguarding human, animal, and environmental health, preserving natural resources and biodiversity and mitigating climate change.

By focusing on implementing a resilient and sustainable agri-food system through transdisciplinary services offered by research infrastructures, the project will also seek to **actively involve key actors** from the agriculture system in the research process.

#Agroecology
#OpenInnovation
#InterdisciplinaryResearch
#TransdisciplinaryApproach

Addressing current and emerging global challenges

Encouraging interdisciplinary and transdisciplinary approaches

Fostering open Science and innovation

Our Commitments

- * Addressing emerging and global challenges
- * Encouraging interdisciplinary and transdisciplinary approaches
- * Fostering open science and innovation

Our Research Infrastructures

Home > About > Our Research Infrastructures

Our Research Infrastructures

11 RIs at the Heart of AgroServ

AgroServ is an interdisciplinary service provider that gathers 11 recognised research infrastructures and a complementary offer of socio-economic expertise. This interdisciplinary consortium of leading researchers to study agrosystems adopting a holistic and multi-scale approach.

To do so, it will offer them complementary and customised research services such as: crop trials, animal model resistance, emerging pest and diseases, soil health, climate change resilience, animal health and welfare, water cycle, smart agriculture, smart innovation, rural communities. This wide portfolio of services spans all scales: the micro-ecosystem (organism level); the plant-organism level, the ecosystem level and the society level.

The 11 RIs at the heart of AgroServ: [ANAE-ERIC](#), [ELIXIR](#), [EMBRC](#), [EU-OPENSOURCE ERIC](#), [EMPHASIS](#), [EMBRC-ERIC](#), [EMPHASIS](#), [EMBRC-ERIC](#), [EMBRC-ERIC](#), [EMBRC-ERIC](#), [EMBRC-ERIC](#), [EMBRC-ERIC](#).

AnaEE-ERIC	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>
ELIXIR	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>
EMBRC-ERIC	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>
EMPHASIS	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>
EU-OPENSOURCE ERIC	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>
Euro-Biomaging	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>
IBISBA	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>
LifeWatch-ERIC	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>
METROFOOD-RI	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>
MIRRI-ERIC	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>
SmartCow	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>

Our Research Infrastructures

- * A text presenting the consortium
- * A list of the 11 RIs at the heart of AgroServ
- * A presentation of each RI + contact details

— Our European Partners
Home • ABOUT • Our European Partners

Our European Partners

More than 70 EU partners supporting AgroServ

AgroServ gathers more than 70 partners concerning a high impact potential. Partnerships are needed in the context of transdisciplinary research. Through the provision of diverse scientific skills, highly specialised expertise and experimental skills and laboratories, AgroServ will continue to strengthen its collaboration with its partners to ensure long-term cooperation.

Browse by EU country

- Austria

- Belgium

- Bulgaria

- Czech Republic

- Denmark

- Finland

- France

- Germany

- Greece

- Italy

- Ireland

- Lithuania

- The Netherlands

- Norway

- Poland

- Portugal

- Romania

- Serbia

- Slovenia

- Spain

- Sweden

- Switzerland

- United Kingdom

- + Other partner European institutions and infrastructures

**A list of the
partners
covering
Europe**

*** Presentation and contact
information**

Organisation and Contact

[Home](#) • [ABOUT](#) • [Organisation and Contact](#)

Organisation and Contact

An integrated approach to support agroecological research in the long-term

All the activities developed under AgroServ, from the provision of research services to community building and living labs activities, aim to expand our knowledge on agroecology and provide a wider understanding of the functioning of sustainable agro-systems in the long-term in order to contribute to the European Green Deal (EGD) and to the Sustainable Development Goals (SDGs). To ensure quality and efficiency of the implementation of the different tasks and services, AgroServ is structured around nine Work Packages (WP).

Contact: contact@agroserv.eu

- Work Package 1: Integrated framework for TransNational Access (TNA) ▼

- Work Package 2: Catalogue integration and customisation of services ▼

- Work Package 3: Integrated data management and analysis ▼

- Work Package 4: Access quality and ethics ▼

- Work Package 5: Community building & users engagement ▼

- Work Package 6: Open innovation hub (Living Labs) ▼

- Work Package 7: Long-term sustainability (beyond 2027) ▼

- Work Package 8: Communication & outreach ▼

- Work Package 9: Project management ▼

Contact the central hub

AgroServ Central Hub
AnAEE-ERIC, CNRS Campus, Bâtiment 11
1 Av. de la Terrasse, 91190 Drigny-Yvette, France

+33 1 69 82 34 06

Email: contact@agroserv.eu

AgroServEU	imen.benmahmoud@ansae.eu
Subject	
Message	

[Send Message](#)

Organisation and Contact

* A presentation of the AgroServ central hub and the different nine work packages

* Contact details

Explore our Catalogue

[Home](#) • [RESEARCH SERVICES](#) • [Explore our Catalogue](#)

Explore our Catalogue

AgroServ, an interdisciplinary service provider

AgroServ enables access to 143 research installations across Europe for researchers from academia and the industry. The installations can be used for experiments with scientific or technological objectives to answer basic and applied questions related to sustainable and resilient agriculture and agroecological transitions.

Scientists can use these services and facilities to address diverse research questions to simulate current and future climatic conditions, test new management practices, assess the performance of crops under changing conditions etc.

These services and installations, where experimentation, analysis and observation can be performed, are managed by the 11 research infrastructures that constitute the AgroServ Consortium. They include access to virtual and experimental tools and installations addressing basic and applied research.

[Browse the catalogue of services](#)

Explore our Catalogue

*** Presentation of the catalogue and the link to access it**

Explore our Guidelines

[Home](#) • [RESEARCH SERVICES](#) • [Explore our Guidelines](#)

Explore our Guidelines

[Resources to better access and use our platforms](#)

You can find on this page a list of resources that can help you better use and access our platforms. Note that we are currently updating this page with the relevant materials. If you have a question, visit our FAQs page and/or reach out to our central access manager:

<https://agroserv.eu/calls-and-applications/frequently-asked-questions>

Explore our Guidelines

*** The different guidelines that will be made available for scientists and access providers, etc.**

You are a researcher and you want to send a proposal to access our research services?

You are an access provider managing installations and you need to update your installation or service information on our catalogue of services (ISIA Platform)?

You are experiencing a technical problem on our platforms?

You want to share your feedback about the catalogue to help us improve it?

Scientific Domains

Home • RESEARCH SERVICES • Scientific Domains

Natural Sciences

Biological, Medical and Health Sciences

Chemistry and Material Sciences

Agricultural Sciences

Microbiology

Engineering, Information Science and Technology

Humanities and Social Sciences

Earth & Environmental Sciences

For more information on the scientific domains and subdomains covered...

Explore our catalogue of research services

Scientific Domains

* More than 8 scientific domains covered

Application Procedure

Home • RESEARCH SERVICES • Application Procedure

Application Procedure

145 installations across Europe open to researchers from academia and the industry

The goal of AgroServ is to support research and innovation by providing exceptional and integrated research services in Europe with the goal to advance sustainability and resilient agriculture and support agroecological transitions.

The application to access our research facilities is a two-step process:

- 1st Step: Pre-proposal submission (expression of interest)
Deadline: 23rd of October 2023, 12:00 am CEST
- 2nd Step: Full proposal submission (final research project)
Deadline: TO BE CONFIRMED

For information see:

- Research facilities: [Catalogue of Services](#)
- Application submission: [Application Portal](#)

IMPORTANT: Please read this page carefully prior to submitting your proposals.

Eligibility: Who is eligible to apply?	✓
Access: How to obtain access to use the AgroServ research services?	✓
Evaluation: How will proposals be evaluated and selected?	✓
Funding and expenses: What are the different funding schemes?	✓
Reporting: How will reporting be conducted once access is granted?	✓
Publication: How to publish and disseminate the results?	✓

Contact us

Dr Heba Ibrahim
Coord. access manager

Application Procedure

* Deadlines and procedures related to the AgroServ Calls for proposals: eligibility, access, evaluation, funding and expenses, reporting, publication

* Contact details

Ethics and Data Policy

[Home](#) • [CALLS AND APPLICATIONS](#) • [Ethics and Data Policy](#)

Ethics and Data Policy

Findable, Accessible, Interoperable and Reusable Data

Data generated within the framework of the AgroServ transnational access scheme shall be **findable, accessible, interoperable and reusable** (following the **FAIR standard**). Depending on the nature of the data, these data shall be accessed and analysed by any groups inside and outside the AgroServ consortium and will be used to **inform evidence-based policymaking**. Additionally, AgroServ's open and FAIR-compliant data will remain accessible in the long term, integrated with significant European initiatives such as the **EOSC**.

The Data Management Plan (**DMP**) shall help partners to manage data, meet funder requirements, and facilitate multiple use of data by the scientific community. It includes information on data handling, data property and on the standards used for storing, curating and sharing data.

Additionally, scientists who have their proposals selected to access the AgroServ research services will need to develop a DMP based on the specific set of services which are being accessed.

Once proposals are pre-selected (pre-application phase), support will be provided for the development of a DMP through workshops and webinars:

In general, the DMP should include, among others:

- ✔ Data description and sources
- ✔ How data will be collected, structured, stored
- ✔ How data will be made accessible for the purpose of analysis and re-use
- ✔ Standards for data identification, file formats, and workflows

[Data Management Plan](#)

Ethics and Data Policy

- * FAIR Principles
- * Data Management Plans

Frequently Asked Questions

[Home](#) • [CALLS AND APPLICATIONS](#) • [Frequently Asked Questions](#)

Frequently Asked Questions

An expert team to answer your questions...

You can find a number of frequently asked questions about our calls for proposals and applications on this page. Please read them carefully. For more information and queries, you can reach out to our contact access manager (see contact details below). For general information about the project, please refer to our contact details on our homepage.

Can I apply for access if I am not from a EU member state or a EU associated country?

How do I know which research service is best-suited for my research?

How do I know if my research falls within the scope of AgroServ?

How do I apply for access to use the AgroServ research facilities?

Can I apply for multiple services simultaneously?

How are applications evaluated and selected?

What happens if my application is successful?

[Contact us](#)

Frequently Asked Questions

- * A list of FAQs that will be updated: questions often asked in relation to the calls for proposals and the application to access the AgroServ research services and installations.

— Newsroom

Home • OUTREACH AND IMPACT • Newsroom

AgroServ Launches its 1st Call for Proposals

Applications are now open for researchers interested in accessing the AgroServ research services and installations

Read the article →

.02 < >

AgroServ Launches its 1st Call for Proposals Open to Scientists

Newsroom

* All news, articles, feature stories and interviews can be found in this section.

— Knowledge Transfer

Home • OUTREACH AND IMPACT • Knowledge Transfer

Knowledge Transfer

Enabling transdisciplinarity and co-creation through the living labs approach

Co-creation has recently become an extremely widespread and popularised term. It's not only used on consumer-centred discourse but also on multi-stakeholders' platforms such as public-private partnerships and living labs involving innovation and research.

Co-creation in the private sectors is described as the process of value creation through the active collaboration of the consumers by allowing them to co-develop the product and service experience to fit their needs (Kambil et al. 1999).

In the context of the AgroServ project, co-creation should be aligned with the living labs co-creation concept which refers to a form of open innovation, where the creation of new value takes place in cooperation between the experts and a variety of stakeholders from industry, research, public institutions, and civil society, in which the inputs of the user play a central role (Hagy et al. 2016, Mambirini-Doudet et al. 2021).

Therefore, the involvement of multiple stakeholders creates a multi-contextual scene in which the actors engage and interact with other stakeholders during every step of the co-creation process from problem definition to piloting (Ballon et al. 2005, Kreiling and Paunov 2021). This can mobilise and bring together complementary and transversal agroecological expertise which increases the speed and uptake of innovations while also increasing awareness and relevance of agroecological transition and, at the same time, addressing socio-economic challenges via the involvement of civil society.

Knowledge Transfer

* Transdisciplinarity and living labs in the context of AgroServ.

— Scientific publications

Home • OUTREACH AND IMPACT • Scientific Publications

Scientific Publications

You are a researcher and you have been granted access to the AgroServ services as part of your research? You are required to acknowledge the support of the AgroServ project (infrastructures & data).

Peer-reviewed communications

⇒ Your work has been selected to be published in a peer-reviewed journal, published in edited volumes, books, or reports, communicated during conferences or patent announcements, etc.

⇒ As soon as your publication is accepted, you must: Notify the AgroServ communications officer and make sure to include them in the exchanges from the early stages of drafting press releases and communication supports, and this for coordination purposes.

Popular / General communications

⇒ Your work has been: covered by the press or was featured in the media, etc.

⇒ As soon as the article or interview is published - Share with us the link and a news brief.

Scientific Publications

* All future publications and relate guidelines will be published on this page

The next steps...

Social media: LinkedIn & X-Twitter

The twitter and LinkedIn accounts were created in March 2023. Both were used to launch the communication about the first conference organised by AgroServ: the European Research Services on Agroecology Conference (ERSAC2023).

Channel	Date of creation	Number of subscribers
LinkedIn	30/03/2023	343
X-Twitter	30/03/2023	95
YouTube	01/06/2023	For internal use to publish internal videos for the time being. It will evolve to include other public and external materials.

Funded by
the European Union

Edit profile

AgroServ EU
@AgroServEU

EU-funded project 🌱 Sowing the seeds of #research in #Agroecology 🌱
Integrated services supporting a #Sustainable #AgroecologicalTransition 🌱
📍 Europe 🔗 [linkedin.com/company/agroserve/](https://www.linkedin.com/company/agroserve/) 📅 Joined March 2023
118 Following 95 Followers

AgroServ EU

EU-funded project 🌱 Sowing the seeds of research in Agroecology 🌱
Research Services - 343 followers

AgroServ EU
Research Services

EU-funded project 🌱 Sowing the seeds of research in Agroecology 🌱

Follow

About us

Agriculture improves health and wellbeing. It contributes to local food security, increases farmers' incomes and helps reduce poverty. However, developing a resilient and sustainable agricultural system can be challenging. Success hinges on a deep understanding of the systems and their interactions with the environment. The EU-funded AgroServ project will study the threats and challenges and deepen our understanding of how to achieve a resilient and sustainable agrifood system. This transdisciplinary project will bring together all actors of the agriculture system. Farmers are the first, thanks to a wide offer of living labs across Europe. By delivering a Europe-wide data ecosystem, AgroServ aims to grow the agroecology research community and support the cross-fertilisation of knowledge.

🌐 <https://twitter.com/AgroServEU>
✉ contact@agroserv.eu

Website	https://agroserv.eu/ 🌐
Industry	Research Services
Company size	2-10 employees
Type	Public Company
Founded	2022
Specialties	Agroecology, Agricultural sciences, Ecology, Forestry, Fisheries, Agronomy, Plant Protection, Sustainable Agriculture, Natural Sciences, Biological Sciences, Ecosystems, Social Sciences, Economics, and BusinessManagement

A selection of posts published on LinkedIn and their organic impressions

<p>AgroServ EU 343 followers 5mo • Edited •</p> <p>[Webinar] Ahead of its first annual conference, the #HorizonEurope project #AgroServ is pleased to invite you to its first #webinar on #EuropeanResearchServices on #Agroecology that will take place on the ...see more</p> <p>60 2 comments • 26 reposts</p> <p>Like Comment Repost</p>	<p>AgroServ EU 343 followers 5mo • Edited •</p> <p>What #integrated and #transdisciplinary #research services to accelerate #AgroecologicalTransitions? ...see more</p> <p>69 2 comments • 35 reposts</p> <p>Like Comment Repost</p>																		
<p>Organic impressions: 2,592 Impressions Hide results</p>	<p>Organic impressions: 2,849 Impressions Hide results</p>																		
<p>Post performance Targeted to: All followers</p> <table border="1"> <tr> <td>2,592 Impressions</td> <td>149 Engagements</td> <td>5.75% Engagement rate</td> </tr> <tr> <td>61 Clicks</td> <td>2.35% Click-through rate</td> <td>60 Reactions</td> </tr> <tr> <td>2 Comments</td> <td>26 Reposts</td> <td></td> </tr> </table>	2,592 Impressions	149 Engagements	5.75% Engagement rate	61 Clicks	2.35% Click-through rate	60 Reactions	2 Comments	26 Reposts		<p>Post performance Targeted to: All followers</p> <table border="1"> <tr> <td>2,849 Impressions</td> <td>224 Engagements</td> <td>7.86% Engagement rate</td> </tr> <tr> <td>118 Clicks</td> <td>4.14% Click-through rate</td> <td>69 Reactions</td> </tr> <tr> <td>2 Comments</td> <td>35 Reposts</td> <td></td> </tr> </table>	2,849 Impressions	224 Engagements	7.86% Engagement rate	118 Clicks	4.14% Click-through rate	69 Reactions	2 Comments	35 Reposts	
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AgroServ EU

343 followers

1w • Edited •

You are a Researcher, PhD student or Master's student from academia and/or the industry and you are interested in working on projects that address [#interdisciplinary](#) topics related to [#agroecology](#)? [...see more](#)

AgroServ Launches its First Call for Proposals Open to Scientists from Academia and the Industry

Send your pre-proposals by

October 23rd, 2023, 12:00 am CEST

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and 56 others

6 comments • 33 reposts

Like

Comment

Repost

Organic impressions: 3,857 Impressions

Hide results

Post performance

Targeted to: All followers

3,857

Impressions

197

Engagements

5.11%

Engagement rate

116

Clicks

3.01%

Click-through rate

57

Reactions

6

Comments

18

Reposts

A selection of three posts published on Twitter and their organic impressions:

Editorial calendar: current priorities

The AgroServ first Call for Proposals has been published on the AgroServ website. Following the launch of the website and the publication of the call, we have identified the following priorities:

Articles presenting the services and the thematic focus of the project (interviews, feature stories, etc.) will be published on the website. Once published, these articles will be shared on the different social media channels to engage with the AgroServ network.

An AgroServ Booklet presenting the consortium and the different research services will be shared on the different digital communication channels and will be used during external events.

Tutorial Videos & guidelines (website and social media)

- Tutorial video 1: how to explore the catalogue of services + simple pdf guideline doc
- Tutorial video 2: how to send a proposal (steps, etc.) + simple pdf guideline doc

Video glossary of technical terms

Video of Q/As

General communication and dissemination videos:

- Video 1: introducing AgroServ (consortium, network, objectives, etc.)
- Video 2: Introducing the Living Labs approach

2022
2027

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